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Review Article

SONOGRAPHIC EVALUATION OF ADENOMYOSIS AND ITS IMPACT ON FEMALE FERTILITY - A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract:

Background: Adenomyosis is a most common benign gynecological disease that is identified by intrusion of endometrium in to myometrium and is associated with presenting symptoms of pelvic pain, dysmenorrhea and menorrhagia. It causes diffuse enlargement of uterus and mostly affects the women in late reproductive age. Adenomyosis has an unclear etiology and remains asymptomatic in some patients so diagnosis and treatment remains an immense challenge. Furthermore most of the time adenomyosis co-exist with other relevant gynaecological pathologies including endometriosis and uterine leiomyomas so sensitivity and specificity of transvaginal ultrasound and MRI remain uncertain. Adenomyosis affects the women of reproductive age and has great impact on quality of life and female fertility. The most effective and non-invasive tool in routine gynaecological examination and diagnosis of adenomyosis is transvaginal ultrasound.

Objective: The main objective of this study was to evaluate the diagnosis of adenomyosis with Sonography and to describe its impact on fertility and women reproduction.

Method: An electronic based search is made on Google scholar using key words "Adenomyosis", "Sonography" and "fertility". The relevant articles from different journals including (Pubmed, Science Direct, Bio Med, ncbi, tandfonline) and others included. The articles were selected from 2002 to 2020 and consist of retrospective study, cross sectional study and systematic review. The selected articles were assessed for study plan and further discussion and systematic review is made.

Results: Most of the studies concluded that adenomyosis can be diagnosed by a combination of clinical history and Transvaginal Ultrasonography, which is the primary imaging equipment for the diagnosis of adenomyosis. Adenomyosis plays a crucial role in fertile women and is a widespread pathology that has a negative impact on female reproduction and fertility.

Conclusion: With increased number of advances and upgradation of imaging modalities adenomyosis diagnosis is not dependent on surgical methods as it was done before by hysterectomy. Transvaginal sonography (2D & 3D) is one of the most accurate, non invasive and important criteria for the evaluation of adenomyosis and its widespread use in recent era allowed us to improve our pattern towards the diagnosis and management of the disease. Adenomyosis is one of the most challenging pathology as its etiology and true incidence is still unknown and prevalence varies widely depending on diagnostic criteria. Adenomyosis has a negative impact on female fertility and is highly associated with increased risk of infertility, primary infertility in case of focal adenomyosis. Predominantly detected in female of late reproductive age (fourth and fifth decade of life). Adenomyosis is also associated with miscarriages, preterm delivery, reduced implantation and rate of fertility in patients with IVF treatment.

Keywords: Ultrasonography, Adenomyosis, Fertility

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INTRODUCTION:

Adenomyosis is a benign disease of the uterus which is described as existence of ectopic endometrial glands and stroma in the myometrium. The term “adeno” means ectopic endometrial glands and term “myosis” means muscular hyperplasia/ hypertrophy. Relocation of endometrial cells in to myometrium is followed by a muscular hyperplasia. Causing thickening of the junctional zone which leads to diffuse enlargement of uterine cavity. Adenomyosis can be divided in to two-integral parts of the disorder which constitute heterotopic endometrial glands and stroma and second muscular element. Adenomyosis is often seen together with endometriosis and usually affects the women of late reproductive age. The clinical manifestations of adenomyosis include pelvic pain, menorrhagia, dysmenorrhea and dyspareunia. Some patients may remain asymptomatic so these symptoms are non specific and can also present with other gynaecological disorders. The diagnosis of adenomyosis was made on the basis of histological findings during early periods. But now a days with recent advances in imaging modalities and by means of non invasive techniques the diagnosis of adenomyosis is much more accurate and can be achieved without surgical procedures such as hysterectomy. Imaging modalities including Ultrasonography and MRI gives more easy, approachable and non invasive methods with high sensitivity and specificity for the efficient interpretation of the disease. Transvaginal Ultrasonography(2D,3D) is one of the most common, specific and crucial non invasive diagnostic tool which provides high diagnostic accuracy for discernment of site and location of adenomyosis. Sonographic appearance of adenomyosis is variable uterus may appear diffusely enlarged with poorly defined areas of abnormal echotexture which represent thickening of junctional zone, myometrium may appear heterogeneous with hypoechoic areas with presence or absence of cysts. Adenomyosis appears as

areas of reduced echogenicity or as heterogenous myometrium on transvaginal ultrasound. The regions of reduced echogenicity represents areas of smooth muscle hyperplasia and heterogenous regions represents heterotopic endometrial tissue surrounded by smooth muscle. The presence of heterotopic endometrial tissue and its ratio to smooth muscle determines the sonographic appearance of adenomyosis. Other sonographic features include hyperechoic islands or striations, irregular endometrial-myometrial junction, tiny anechoic myometrial cysts, cystic striations. The presence of dilated cystic glands or hemorrhagic foci within the heterotopic endometrial tissue occurs in the presence of small myometrial cysts (less than 5mm in diameter). In case of cystic adenomyosis the presence of hemorrhage within the ectopic endometrial gland is more broad and cystic anechoic spaces seen within the myometrium are of variable size and can occur throughout the myometrium. Adenomyosis causes mass effect and represents an abnormal structure or heterogenous texture of uterus. The focal adenomyosis represents as regions of myometrial thickening, and can also represent as heterogenous mildly echogenic focal nodules with indistinct margins and cystic spaces. Adenomyosis increases uterine vascularity and on Color Doppler scans shows penetrating tortuous vessels throughout the myometrium. Adenomyosis is most common relevant comorbidity during evaluation of infertility. Many studies with limited data analysis supported the relation between adenomyosis and infertility. Most of the evidences supported the cause that adenomyosis has a negative impact on fertility. Reproductive outcome is significantly affected and abridged in patients with adenomyosis. Adenomyosis is also associated with reduced birth rate, pregnancy rate, preterm delivery and decreased implantation. Adenomyosis also influence the patient treatment for infertility such as IVF and causes negative effect on fertility.

These are Sagittal transvaginal USG images of adenomyosis representing sonographic appearance and features of adenomyosis, this classification presented by Bromley et al in 2000. (Image courtesy Pinterest)

STUDY SELECTION:

Multiple articles searched on Google scholar were selected, reviewed and analyzed for assessment of study plan. Prospective study were excluded from the data analysis, only retrospective and cross sectional studies were included. The articles published from 2002 to 2020 relevant to the title were selected and analyzed for the literature review.

RESULTS:

By using search methods 20 research articles were selected on the basis of title, abstract and conclusion. The selected articles were assessed and reviewed in its full version, systematically organized the collected data and results are concluded on Sonographic evaluation of adenomyosis and its impact on fertility.

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW:

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the sonographic diagnosis of adenomyosis and its impact on fertility. Most of the studies emphasized the role of Ultrasonography for evaluation of adenomyosis and its corresponding relation to infertility.

In 2003 Roland Devlieger and others conducted a comparative review-based study in which different articles from previous studies were analyzed for the purpose of discussion on uterine adenomyosis as a co factor in female fertility, the clinical presentation of adenomyosis is reviewed as well as recent developments in non-invasive imaging modalities for the pathology. Also, different treatment techniques discussed for the purpose of review. The presenting symptoms which consist of menorrhagia (40-50%), dysmenorrhea (10-30%) and other symptoms like pelvic pain and dyspareunia were found. In a study of 26 patients with infertility and menorrhagia or dysmenorrhea adenomyosis was found in (53.8%).¹

In 2017 Margit Dueholm done a data analysis review-based study on fertility outcome in patients with adenomyosis and review of reproductive outcome in patients treated with IVF for infertility. The author conducted a PubMed search and Articles related to title were selected, in all 726 abstracts were analyzed and 277 articles were included for assessment of study

and indexed. These studies indicate an increase in adverse implantation outcome in consequence to the extent of junctional zone changes in adenomyosis. The use of imaging gives 23-28% false negative results in highly symptomatic women scheduled for hysterectomy according to this study.²

In 2017 Roberto Marci and others conducted study on the basis of articles review, a manual search on PubMed is made for articles and selected articles were assessed for study analysis. All the selected articles were assessed for study design, diagnosis of adenomyosis and post treatment reproductive outcome. They concluded that adenomyosis is most common gynaecological pathology with a negative impact on fertility.³

In 2018 Ryan K. Cunningham and others conducted a comparative article review based analysis. In this study they highlighted the pathophysiology of adenomyosis and its correlation to ultrasound findings. The first report of adenomyosis imaging diagnosis was made in 1949 using hysterosalpingography (HSG), however due to its low sensitivity, HSG was never used as a primary diagnostic tool for adenomyosis. The imaging diagnosis of adenomyosis was not accurate until the advent of MRI. However a study by Reinhold et al reported that transvaginal US was as accurate as MRI. In this comparison study which used the histopathology of hysterectomy specimens as the standard, found no statistical difference between sensitivity and specificity of transvaginal US and MRI, transvaginal US 89% and 89% and MRI 86% and 86% respectively. Transvaginal ultrasound should be considered the primary imaging modality for the diagnosis of adenomyosis because of its widespread availability and lower cost comparative to other techniques.⁴

This systematic review article was presented in 2018 by Taina Pezzin, Rocha and others. The main objective of this article was to evaluate relation between adenomyosis and reproductive outcome after fertility sparing treatment for adenomyosis associated infertility. Adenomyosis is a crucial factor for causing infertility either by leading towards early miscarriages, or by impaired implantation. They conducted a search in PubMed/Medline and 16 articles were selected, studies examined surgical treatments of adenomyosis. Considering only spontaneous pregnancies the overall clinical pregnancy rate was very low (18.2%). Ten studies presented that reproductive techniques for infertility associated to adenomyosis showed long stimulation protocol had better outcomes compared to short stimulation protocol in pregnancy rate (43.3%

vs 31.8%; $P=0.001$), live births (43.0% vs 23.1%; $P=0.005$) and miscarriage (18.5% vs 31.1%; $P<0.0001$).⁵

In 2014 a retrospective study was conducted by Giuseppe Benagiano to evaluate the life cycle approach for adenomyosis. This study evaluated the features of adenomyosis at different stages of a women reproductive system. According to this study adenomyosis mostly affects the adult women. Active adenomyosis has been found in pre and peri menopausal women and in postmenopausal women receiving tamoxifen. The specificity of a preoperative diagnosis of adenomyosis based clinical findings is poor, ranging from 2-26%. Analyzed data from 14 selected studies and found that adenomyosis was more common in women with heavy bleeding (31.9%), the probability of adenomyosis in a women with heavy bleeding and positive ultrasound features were (68.1%).⁶

A Meta-analysis and systematic review was presented by Grace Younes in 2017 on effects of adenomyosis and IVF treatment outcomes for infertility. This systematic review was made on the basis of search made on Google Scholar and PubMed all the selected articles were reviewed and analysed. 11 comparative studies were evaluated for the clinical outcomes of IVF treatments in women with and without adenomyosis, diagnosed with the use of MRI and transvaginal Ultrasonography. This study concluded that rates of implantation, clinical pregnancy, and live births are significantly decreased in patients with adenomyosis. And also concluded that rate of miscarriages are higher in women with adenomyosis.⁷

In 2006 Shetal Chopra and others conducted A 3 year data based research on 80 women who had done pelvic MRI and TVS scan in a period of 6 months interval. The images were retrospectively reviewed for assessment of adenomyosis. They concluded that adenomyosis was identified in 45 patients out of 80 on MRI, it was diagnosed on Ultrasonography in 33 patients (73%). All the women who presented for the adenomyosis had a history of pelvic pain, abnormal bleeding or both. They also concluded that adenomyosis is most common in premenopausal women. The reported sensitivity and specificity of TVS for diagnosis of adenomyosis was ranged from 53% to 89% and 67% to 78% respectively.⁸

In 2017 a retrospective study was done by Vered H. Eisenberg and others to identify the prevalence of sonographic features for the evaluation of adenomyosis in women who have undergone a surgery

for endometriosis. A retrospective case control study performed on 94 and 60 women respectively who present with history of severe pain or infertility, or women who have a history of laproscopic surgery and in which transvaginal ultrasound was performed compared with a group of healthy women. It was concluded that sonographic features of adenomyosis are highly prevalent in women who have undergone surgery for endometriosis. A significant number of sonographic features of adenomyosis were found to be associated with increased risk of infertility, regardless of endometriosis severity.⁹

In 2012 Sebastiano Campo and others conducted a Systematic review-based study on the accurate diagnosis of adenomyosis and possible correlation between adenomyosis and infertility. They presented that with the advances in imaging techniques it is possible to make accurate diagnosis of adenomyosis, and also its clinical correlation with infertility.¹⁰

This systematic review and meta-analysis was conducted in 2017 by H Krentel and others. A Pub Med search was made and selected articles were analyzed for clinical symptoms and diagnostic evaluation of adenomyosis. They concluded that in past diagnosis of adenomyosis was made by hysterectomy with a report rate of more than 30% adenomyosis in hysterectomy specimens. Salim et al. reported 50% decrease in pregnancy rate, and Vercellini et al. 68% reduction in pregnancy in women associated with adenomyosis. They also concluded that adenomyosis is associated with presenting symptoms such as, dysmenorrhea, menorrhagia and chronic pelvic pain with a rate of 81.7% dysmenorrheal most common presenting complaint. Transvaginal Ultrasonography (TVS), was concluded as most important diagnostic tool with a sensitivity range from 65 to 81%, and specificity from 65 to 100%.¹¹

In 2020 a systematic review article and meta-analysis was presented by Konstantinos Nirgianakis and others on fertility, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes in patients with adenomyosis. This study aimed to identify the association of adenomyosis with fertility. A PubMed and MENDLINE search was made to assess the relevant articles. Out of which 17 articles were selected and it was evaluated that adenomyosis significantly associated with lower clinical pregnancy rate (Odds ratio 0.69; 95% confidence interval 0.51-0.94) and higher miscarriage rate (OR 2.17; 95% CI 1.25-3.79) after treatment with assisted reproductive technology (ART).¹²

In 2019 Paolo Vercellini and others conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis based study on adenomyosis and its association with infertility. According to this review adenomyosis has a detrimental impact on IVF clinical outcomes, as it is associated with reduced rate of implantation (OR=0.66; 95% CI, 0.49-0.88) and pregnancy (OR=0.75; 95% CI, 0.61-0.93), increased risk of miscarriage and consequently a decrease in live birth rates.¹³

In 2020 H. Krentel and R. L. De Wilde conducted a literature review based study on adenomyosis diagnostic evaluation and its treatment. The main objective of this study was to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of different imaging techniques and treatment approach for patients with infertility. They concluded that adenomyosis can be diagnosed with transvaginal Ultrasonography and combination of clinical history, various treatment options are available to reduce symptoms and increase fertility. Adenomyosis has a negative impact on fertility. Diagnostic findings can be change in relation to patient age, hormonal treatment and menstrual cycle.¹⁴

In 2015 Elisabetta Garavaglia and others conducted a review based comparative study on adenomyosis and its impact on women fertility. A PubMed search is made and collected articles were assessed for further evaluation. They concluded that prevalence of adenomyosis which was estimated from literature review is approximately 5-70%. Adenomyosis is difficult to differentiate from other pathologies because its exact etiology is still unknown. Clinical features including dysmenorrhea, (30%), enlarged uterus and menorrhagia (50%) can be seen in other pathologies. This disease can also coexist with other pathologies such as endometriosis (70%), leiomyomas (50%), endometrial hyperplasia (35%), endometrial polyps (2%) and endometrial carcinoma. Adenomyosis may affect young women and have a great impact on their fertility through different pathways.¹⁵

In 2016 J.M. Puente and others conducted a cross sectional study on 1015 patients undergoing ART from January 2009 to December 2013 for 3D Ultrasonography to complete study prior to initiating an ART cycle, after ≥ 3 IVF failures, or ≥ 2 miscarriages at diagnostic imaging unit affiliated with university private IVF center. The prevalence of adenomyosis was 24.4% in women aged ≥ 40 and 22% in women aged < 40 . The presence of adenomyosis has shown to be associated with endometriosis 35.1%. Its prevalence was higher in women with cases of

pregnancy loss 38.2%. Adenomyosis is a clinical condition with a high prevalence that is diagnosed as a primary finding in patients with infertility.¹⁶

DISCUSSION:

The overall assessment of study concluded that adenomyosis is one of the most common gynaecological pathology which present in women of late reproductive age or premenopausal women. The presenting clinical symptoms include menorrhagia, pelvic pain, dyspareunia and dysmenorrhea. The exact etiology of adenomyosis still under consideration and many women remain asymptomatic for a long period of time so examination and diagnosis of adenomyosis is quite challenging. Adenomyosis was diagnosed by surgical procedures during early days, and only way to made exact diagnosis was by means of hysterectomy. But now with invention and advances in recent imaging modalities it is no more a histopathological based diagnosis. Transvaginal Ultrasonography is one of the best and non invasive diagnostic tool now a days. It is more preferable than other imaging modalities such as MRI because it is inexpensive, easy approachable have a high accuracy rate in diagnosis of adenomyosis. Its sensitivity is (80-86%) and specificity is (50-96%) and overall accuracy rate is 68-86% which is almost equal to MRI. Sonographic features of adenomyosis includes diffusely enlarged uterus with areas of decreased echogenicity or heterogeneous myometrium which corresponds to muscular hyperplasia, asymmetrical myometrial thickening, thickening of junctional zone. Adenomyosis and its impact on women reproduction is quite crucial because adenomyosis is becoming a leading and most relevant factor for causing infertility, either by impairing implantation or by causing early miscarriages. It was also reported in many studies that reproductive outcome in patients associated with adenomyosis is significantly reduced. It has a negative impact on female fertility and also on patients treated with IVF for infertility. So overall pregnancy rate is quite low in patients with adenomyosis.

Conflicts Of Interest:

The authors of this study have no affiliations and no corresponding conflict of interest regarding to publication of this article.

Declaration:

This study is not funded by any organization. The authors alone are responsible for content writing and publication of this article.

CONCLUSION:

This study concluded that adenomyosis is one of the most common gynaecological pathology. Which mostly affects the women of late reproductive age with presenting complaints of menorrhagia, chronic pelvic pain, dyspareunia and dysmenorrhea. The exact etiology of adenomyosis is still under consideration and many women remain asymptomatic for a long period of time, so its diagnosis remains a challenging factor for further evaluation. In past times diagnosis of adenomyosis was done on the basis of surgical procedures such as hysterectomy. But now a days with advances in recent imaging modalities the diagnosis of adenomyosis can be made without surgery. Transvaginal Ultrasonography (3D & 2D) is one of the most commonly used and most important non invasive diagnostic imaging technique now a days. Transvaginal Ultrasonography is primary imaging modality which provides a high accuracy with easily available approach and less expensive than other diagnostic procedures. Adenomyosis has a negative impact on female fertility and is associated with reduced implantation and increased miscarriages, So overall pregnancy rate is significantly reduced in patients with adenomyosis. Women with adenomyosis are at higher risk of infertility than those with out this condition.

REFERENCES:

1. Roland Devlieger, Thomas D Hooghe, & Drik Timmerman, "Adenomyosis in infertility clinic", Human Reproduction update, Vol no 9, No 2pp.139-147, Doi:10.1093/humapad/dmg010.
2. Margit Dueholm "Uterine Adenomyosis and infertility", Acta obstetrician at Gynaecologia Scandinavia, Vol 96, Doi:https://doi.org/10.1111/aogs.13158.
3. Roberto Marci, I. Soave, J.M Wenger & Nicola Pluchino (2017). "Treatment options and reproductive outcome for adenomyosis-associated infertility". Current Medical Research and Opinion, Vol.no34(5), pp.839-849. Doi:https://doi.org/10.1080/03007995.2017.1393404.
4. Ryan K. Cunningham, Mindy M. Horrow, Ryan J. Smith & J. Springer, (2018). "Adenomyosis: A Sonographic Diagnosis". Radio Graphics, Vol no38(5), 1576-1589. :https://doi.org/10.1148/rg.2018180080.
5. Rocha, T. P., Andres, M. P., Borrelli, G. M. et al., & Abrão, M. S. (2018). "Fertility-Sparing Treatment of Adenomyosis in Patients With Infertility": A Systematic Review of Current Options. Reproductive Sciences, Vol.no25(4), pp.480-486. https://doi.org/10.1177/1933719118756754.

6. Giuseppe Benagiano, Brosens, I., & M.Habiba, (2015). Adenomyosis: a life-cycle approach. *Reproductive BioMedicine Online*, Vol.no30(3), pp.220–232. [:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rbmo.2014.11.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rbmo.2014.11.005)
7. Grace Younes M.D, Togas Tulandi M.D, M.H.CH (2017). “Effect of adenomyosis on in vitro fertilization treatment outcomes”. *Vol.no108 (3)*,pp.483-490.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fertnstert.2017.06.025>
8. Sheetal Chopra., Lev-Toaff, Anna S.,Ors, F., & D. Bergin,(2006). “Adenomyosis: Common and Uncommon Manifestations on Sonography and Magnetic Resonance Imaging”. *Journal of Ultrasound in Medicine*,Vol no. 25(5)pp., 617–627. Doi:<https://doi.org/10.7863/jum.2006.25.5.617>.
9. Vered H. Eisenberg,N. Arbib,Eyal Schiff,M. Goldenberg, Daniel S.Seidman,& D.Soriano (2017). “Sonographic Signs of Adenomyosis Are Prevalent in Women Undergoing Surgery for Endometriosis and May Suggest a Higher Risk of Infertility”. *BioMed Research International*. Vol 2017, pages 9.Doi:<https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/8967803>.
10. Sebastiano Campo, Giuseppe Benagiano. “Adenomyosis and infertility”*Vol.no 24(1)*,pp.35-46.Doi:<http://doi.org/10.1016/j.rbmo.2011.10.003>.
11. H.Krentel,C. Cezar, S.Becker,A. Di Spiezio Sardo, V.Tanos, M.Wallwiener & R.L.De Wilde. “From Clinical Symptoms to MR Imaging :Diagnostic Steps in Adenomyosis”.*Vol 2017*, Doi:<https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/1514029>.
12. Konstantinos Nirgianakis, D.R.Kalaitzopoulos, A. S. Kohl Schwartz, Boris W.Karamer, M.D.Mueller&Martin Mueller. “Fertility, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes of patients with adenomyosis”. *Reproductive Biomedicine Online*, Doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rbmo.2020.09.023>.
13. Paolo Vercellini, Irene Bonfanti &Nicola Berlanda, Vol no14 (6), pp.365-367,Doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/17446651.2019.1697675>.
14. Harald Krentel & Rudy Leon De Wilde. “ Adenomyosis: diagnostics and treatment. Vol no 53, pp.683-688, Doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00129-020-04655-7>.
15. Elisabetta Garavaglia M.D, Serafini Audery, I. Annalisa, F. Stefano, T. Iacopo, Corti Laura & C.Massimo. “ Adenomyosis and its impact on women fertility”. Vol no13, pp.327-336, *Iran J Repord Med*.
16. J.M Puente, A.Fabris, J.Patel, A. Patel, M. Cerrillo, A. Requena & J.A.G. Velasco. “ Adenomyosis in infertile women and role of 3D ultrasound as a marker of severity of the disease.*Reproductive Biology and Endocrinology*, Doi:10.1186/s12958-016-0185-6.